

**RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ORGANIZATIONAL
COMMITMENTS AND WORK MOTIVATION WITH
EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE IN THE CENTRAL OFFICE OF
PT. ANGKASA PURA I (PERSERO) JAKARTA, INDONESIA**

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Abstract:

Employee performance is very essential in an effort to achieve the company's goals. Work motivation and organizational commitment, psychologically, can be assumed to have a meaningful role for the achievement of expected employee performance. This study seeks to observe the contribution of work motivation and organizational commitment to employee performance. The subject of the research was employees of PT Angkasa Pura I (PERSERO) Jakarta. The population consist on 170 employees and the research sample is composed by 118 employees. The sampling technique uses random sampling. The measuring instrument used is the Likert scale of work motivation, organizational commitment using the model scale answer categorization. Based on the results of instrument analysis with Pearson correlation Product Moment with the SPSS version 17.0 for Windows. The valid items of work motivation scale were 25 of 40 items with alpha ranges between 0.391 - 0.583. On the organizational commitment scale, valid items are 27 of 36 items with alpha ranges from 0.291 until 0.705. The Cronbach alpha is used to test the instrument reliability; then, the test results are, the work motivation reliability is 0.854 while the organizational commitment is 0.865. By using Bivariate and Multivariate Correlation techniques and the Pearson Product Moment formula, the calculated result can be used on the first hypothesis, if $r = 0.815$ and $p < 0.05$, then (Ho) rejected and (Ha) accepted. In the second hypothesis, $r = 0.880$ with $p < 0.05$ means, (Ho) rejected and (Ha) accepted. and the third hypothesis if $R = 0.914$; $R^2 = 0.836$; $p < 0.05$ so if (Ho) rejected and (Ha) will be accepted.

Keywords: commitment of organization, work motivation and performance

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1. Introduction

1.1 Background Problems

Human Resources are empirically a very substantive aspect in an effort to develop, improve the quality of company performance. Whether it is a company in services or industry, the quality of human resources is initially based on an educational background and this is a requirement that must be fulfilled by employees, which of course is in accordance with the type, level, level of employment. The quality of human resources becomes a necessity in an effort to improve company performance. Today's companies are very competitive in various aspects. Especially, this will be observed in terms of the quality of the results of the business produced by the company. One of the measures is the customer's satisfaction.

Human Resources are the most important factor in an organization or company, full involvement of human resources will appear in the form of quality workforce that contributes to increasing productivity or progress of a company. However, no matter how sophisticated the facilities and infrastructure of a company, without being supported by employee reliability or expertise, the company will not be able to progress and develop. Human Resources have, also, a unique nature that is dynamic; the uniqueness in question is that although the functions carried out are the same but in practice and their application will not be the same, it is related to the human character itself and is supported by the condition of a company. The human character is related to work motivation, competence, organizational culture, organizational commitment, job satisfaction and others.

It is often said that Human Resources are assets that are very important for an organization, or the main key to the success of a company's competition, but what happens instead, is that the Human Resources sometimes become a burden to the survival of a company. Based on the fact that Human Resources are company assets, are those who have high abilities that are in accordance with the needs of the organization, while other factors that play a significant role are work motivation and the ability of employees to practice corporate cultural values in each of their work activities in order to achieve performance optimal. The meaning of performance for employees refers to the ability of employees to carry out their overall duties which are their responsibility. These tasks are usually based on the indicators applied by a company to achieve the success that has been determined and the results will be known that someone of the employee will enter the level of high, middle or low performance.

The performance of an employee is an individual aspect, because each employee has a different level of ability to do his tasks. The work performance system can be used by the manager to measures the employee's performance on their own job position. Performance is an action, not an event. Action performance itself consists of many components and is not a result that can be seen right away. Basically, performance is something that is individual, because each employee has a different level of ability to do their jobs. Performance depends on the combination of ability, effort, and opportunity

obtained. This means that performance is the work of employees in working for a certain period of time and the emphasis is on the work done by employees in a certain period of time. (Timpe, 2003).

“Performance is defined as the record of outcomes produced on the specified job function or activity during a specified time period. The performance of all critical or essential functions. The functions that have to do with the work that are performed and not with the characteristic of the person performing.” (Williams, 2004).

Based on the information above, it can also be interpreted that performance is as a whole the results produced on the function of work or special activities during a special period. The overall performance on the job is equal to the number or average performance of the important job functions. Functions related to the work will be carried out and not carried out with the characteristic performance of individual. The opinion above is supported by the statement of Sunarto (2003) who concludes that high performance can be achieved because of high mutual trust among members - its members means that members trust the integrity, characteristics, and abilities of each other member. To achieve high performance requires a long time to build, requires trust, and demands careful attention from a company must be able to facilitate the growth of organizational culture and understand the importance of making human resources owned can be managed properly.

The phenomenon that the author observed in the employees of PT. Angkasa Pura I (PERSERO) is met in quantity, there are still many work targets that have not been achieved in accordance with work standards and work targets that have been set. The time set for achieving the work target is still delayed and the impact is that the company's performance is not optimal. Many factors can influence employee performance. There are two variables that will be observed in this study, namely organizational commitment and work motivation. Both variables are internal variables that psychologically have an impact on employee performance.

Work motivation is an internal variable that is theoretically thought to have a contribution to employee performance. Conceptually motivation is the result of a number of processes that are *internal* or *external* to an individual, which leads to an attitude of enthusiasm in carrying out certain things (Gray et al., 2005).

Kretner and Kinicki (2000) state that motivation is a psychological process that enhances and directs behavior to achieve goals. Thus, motivation can be explained as a formation of behavior that is influenced by *internal* and *external factors*, which can direct it in achieving what is the goal of the company. This understanding implies that a person can be directed to certain behaviors through stimuli from within and from outside the individual. Internal stimuli usually arise based on educational background, experience and needs. While external stimuli can be driven by leadership factors, work environment, colleagues, compensation and others. Motivation is an impetus that becomes the basis of

someone doing something or working. A person who is highly motivated, namely a person who carries out substantial efforts, to support the production goals of his work unit, and the organization where he works. Someone who is not motivated, only gives minimum effort in terms of work. The concept of motivation is an important concept of study about individual performance. Thus, motivation that creates impulses or circumstances that give rise to encouragement. It can also be said that motivation is a factor that encourages people to act in certain ways. Martoyo (2000) argues that humans, in their habitual activities, have a passion for doing something as long as it can produce something that is considered by itself to have a very valuable value, whose purpose is clearly certain to carry on with life, peace, security and so on.

1.2 Formulation of Problem

Based on the background of the above problems, the problems that will be formulated are as follows:

- 1) Is there a relationship between organizational commitment and the performance of the employees of the head office of PT Angkasa Pura I (PERSERO)?
- 2) Is there a relationship between work motivation and the performance of employees of the head office of PT Angkasa Pura I (PERSERO)?
- 3) Is there a relationship between organizational commitment and work motivation with employee performance at PT. Angkasa Pura I (PERSERO)?

1.3 Hypotheses

- 1) Work motivation is a basic reason, a basic thought or something that comes from internal and external individuals that can cause encouragement or enthusiasm to work hard.
- 2) Organizational commitment is the level of identification and involvement of individuals with and within an organization and does not want to leave the organization because of the establishment of good relationships on the basis of mutual trust.
- 3) Performance is the performance displayed by the employee in accordance with his work unit and expressed in the form of work appraisal.

1.4 Objectives

This study aims to find out:

- 1) The relationship between organizational commitment and employee performance at PT. Angkasa Pura I (PERSERO).
- 2) The relationship between work motivation and employee performance at PT. Angkasa Pura I (PERSERO).
- 3) The relationship between organizational commitment and work motivation with employee performance at PT. Angkasa Pura I (PERSERO).

1.5 Research Benefits

From this study, it is expected to provide the following:

- Theoretical benefits - this research is expected to contribute information to science within the scope of industrial and organizational psychology and can stimulate further assessment especially related to motivational problems, work, organizational commitment and employee performance.
- Practical benefits - it is expected that the results of this study can be useful input for companies, especially for management, how to be able to foster organizational commitment and work motivation of employees positively. So that this in turn can stimulate the performance of employees of employees to work more optimally so that in the end it can provide benefits and benefits for the progress of the company.

2. Understanding Performance

In a large Indonesian dictionary, performance is interpreted as something to be achieved, the achievement shown and the ability of a person. Many limitations are given by experts regarding the term performance, although it differs in the pressure of its formulation, but in principle the performance is about the process of achieving results. The term performance is derived from word "job performance" or "actual performance" (achievement of someone in work life). So, it can be defined that performance is the work of quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him (AA Anwar Prabu Mangkunegara, 2004: 67).

According to Kusnadi (2003; 64), who states that performance is every movement, actions, implementation, activities or actions directed at achieving certain goals or targets. Hariandja (2002; 195) suggests that performance is the result of work achieved by employees or real behavior that is displayed in accordance with its role in the organization. Employee performance is a very important thing in the organization's business to achieve its objectives, so that various activities must be carried out by the organization to improve it.

Whereas, according to Mathis and Jackson (2002: 78), performance is basically what is done, and which is not done by employees. Employee performance affects how much they contribute to the organization. Mathis and Jackson (2002: 8) further provide a person's performance standards that are seen as output quantity, output quality, output period, workplace presence and cooperative attitude. The performance standard is determined based on job criteria, which is to explain what the organization has given to be done by its employees, therefore individual performance in job criteria must be measured, compared to existing standards and the results must be communicated to all employees. Mathis and Jackson (2002: 81) also explain performance standards can be in the form of production output or better known as numerical performance standards and non-numerical performance standards.

2.1 Performance Assessment Objectives

The objectives of performance appraisal, according to Dharma (2001: 150), are as follows:

- Accountability, if standards and targets are used as a measure of accountability, then the basis for making a decision to increase salaries or wages, promotions, special assignments, etc. is quality the work of the employee concerned.
- Development, if standards and targets are used as tools for development purposes, it refers to the support needed by employees in carrying out their work. Support can be in the form of training, guidance, or other assistance.

Every employee in carrying out their duties or duties feels that their work is inseparable from the superior's assessment both directly and indirectly. Performance assessment is used to determine the performance of an employee. According to Rivai (2005: 55), the benefits of performance appraisal are:

A. Benefits for employees assessed include:

- Increasing motivation;
- Increasing job satisfaction;
- The existence of standard clarity of expected results;
- The opportunity to communicate upwards;
- Increasing understanding of personal value.

B. Benefits for assessors:

- Increasing job satisfaction;
- To measure and identify trends in employee performance;
- Increase job satisfaction both from managers and employees;
- As a means of increasing employee motivation;
- Can identify opportunities for employee rotation.

C. Benefits for companies

- Improve all node units in the company;
- Improve communication quality;
- Improve overall employee motivation;
- Increase broad view concerning the tasks performed for each employee.

The elements used in the assessment of employee performance, according to Hasibun (2002: 59), are as follows:

- achievement, assessment of work results both in quality and quantity that can be produced by employees.
- discipline, disciplinary assessment in complying with existing regulations and doing work in accordance with instructions given to him.
- creativity, assessment of the ability of employees to develop creativity to complete their work so they can work more efficiently and effectively.
- working together, assessing the willingness of employees to participate and cooperate with other employees vertically or horizontally inside and outside so that the results of their work are better.

- skills, assessments in uniting and harmonizing the various elements involved in developing policy and in management situations.
- responsibility, assessment of the willingness of employees to take responsibility for their policies, work and results of work, facilities and infrastructure used, and work behavior.

2.2 Factors Affecting Performance

Factors affecting performance is the capability and motivation factors. This is in accordance with the opinion of Keith Davis in Anwar Prabu Mangkunegara (2005: 67) who formulates that:

- Human Performance = Ability + Motivation
- Motivation = Attitude + Situation
- Ability = Knowledge + Skill

According to Mangkunegara (2001: 67-68), the factors that influence someone's performance are:

- the ability factor, in general this ability is formed into two things that are potential abilities (IQ) and abilities reality (knowledge and skills).
- motivational factors, motivation is formed from the attitude of employees in dealing with work situations.

According to M. Nurlaila (2010), as for the factors that influence performance are:

- a) Motivation - it means a condition that encourages or becomes because people do an action that takes place consciously. Motivation has a direct relationship with the individual performance of employees. Because of the position and relationship, it is very strategic if the development of individual employee performance starts from increasing work motivation. Motivation is a regulator of direction or purpose in carrying out activities, so that high motivation will take precedence over the weak.
- b) Capability - in this case, is the individual's ability to work. If the ability is high, the resulting performance will be high but vice versa if the performance is low, it will be low.
- c) Work environment – it refers to aspects that are around the working place and include the work of employees in the office. The conditions of the work environment depend more and are created by the leadership, so the work atmosphere created depends on the pattern created by the leader. The work environment in the company can be in the form of task structure, job design, leadership patterns, cooperation patterns, availability of work facilities, and rewards (reward system).

In addition to paying attention to the above, companies also need to improve the performance of their employees by conducting work division and job enrichment. Expansion of work is the assignment of tasks to employees with a high level of difficulty and risk and usually not so many tasks that are charged while the enrichment of the work

itself is the provision of many tasks to employees but with a level of difficulty and a little risk. And all of that is adjusted to the level of employee ability.

2.3 Operational Definition of Research

According to Sumadi Suryabrata (2002: 76), the operational definition is a definition based on the characteristics of things that are defined which can be observed.

As for the operational definition of this study are as follows:

- Employee Performance - a measure of employee performance in a certain time expressed in the form of numbers. This number shows employee performance.
- Work motivation - a basic reason or something that comes from internal and external individuals that can cause encouragement or enthusiasm to work hard. Measured using a work motivation scale, which includes factors: intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation.
- Organizational Commitment - psychological attachment of individuals, so that individuals are bound in the organization and feel the need for work accompanied by a sense of responsibility towards the organization, also the desire to stay and survive in the company where the employee works. Measured using the scale of organizational commitment, which includes factors: affective commitment, commitment continuity and normative commitment.

2.4 Population, Samples and Sampling Techniques

2.4.1 Population

Research subjects are important things that must be determined before the research activities are carried out. In determining the research subjects, the thing that must be considered is the study population. Population is a generalization area consisting of objects or subjects that have certain strengths and characteristics set by researchers to be studied and then drawn conclusions (Sugiyono, 2003: 55).

The population in this study was the administrative staff of PT Angkasa Pura I (PERSERO) head office in the Risk Management and Compliance department, which amounted to 170 employees, with the following characteristics: having a minimum tenure of one year, this characteristic was used based on the consideration that employees usually have a working period less than one year is an important period in developing work motivation because employees are faced with new environments within the new company.

2.4.2 Samples and Sampling Techniques

Samples are a portion of the number and characteristics possessed by the population (Sugiyono, 2003: 56). Samples taken from the population must be truly representative. Based on the Table Krejcie-Morgan for a population of 170, 118 samples were used, then used for the trial of 30 employees.

Sampling in this study was carried out by *simple random technique*, that is a technique of sampling in any populations, Data samples in this study were taken by simple random technique, separately or as a whole, then the same opportunity was given to become a sample member (Sutrisno Hadi 1994: 75). This technique is used by researchers because sampling for this study was taken randomly regardless of the strata in the population.

2.5 Data Collection Method

Data collection method used in this study is to use the scale method. According to Saifuddin Azwar (2002: 4), the scale has the following characteristics:

- 1) Stimulus in the form of questions or statements that do not directly reveal the attributes to be measured but rather reveal the behavior indicators of the attributes in question.
- 2) Subject answers are some of the many indications regarding the measured attributes, while the final conclusion as a new diagnosis can be achieved if all items have been responded to.
- 3) Subject responses are not classified as true-false answers. All answers can be accepted insofar as they are answered honestly and sincerely. It's just that different answers will be interpreted differently.

The scale referred to in this study is a Likert scale, which is a scale that has a score, from numbers one to five. With alternative answers from five choices, which consist of very suitable (SS), appropriate (S), neutral (N), inappropriate (TS), and very inappropriate (STS) answers.

2.6 Methods of Analysis of Research Instruments

In research, an analysis of the data that has been obtained must be carried out Every study must be tested for validity and reliability to find out whether the items used have measured what should be measured and reliable consistency.

A. Validity

Validity comes from the word validity which has the meaning to what extent the accuracy and accuracy of a measuring instrument in carrying out its measuring function. A test or measuring instrument can be said to have high validity if the instrument carries out its measuring function or gives a measurement result that is in accordance with the mechanism carried out by the measurement. Tests that produce data that are not relevant to the purpose of measurement are said to be tests that have low validity.

Contained here that whether or not a measuring instrument is valid depends on whether or not the measuring instrument reaches the desired measurement objectives correctly (Saifuddin Azwar, 2002: 3). To get the validity, the following are done: validity test. The item validity is used to measure the validity of each item. The way to determine the content of items in this technique is by calculating the correlation coefficient between the item scores and the total score.

B. Correlation Between Factors

Correlation between factors is a complex set of procedures to analyze and explain mutual relations between a limited group of variables called factors, correlation between factors is done because in this study there are more than one factor. How to analyze the correlation between factors is to correlate the scores of each factor and factor score.

2.7 Analysis of Research Results

Analysis of research data was conducted to analyze the relationship between organizational commitment and work motivation with the performance of employees of PT Angkasa Pura I (PERSERO).

Based on the results of research data analysis, the first hypothesis obtained a “r” value of 0.815 with $p < 0.05$. This means (Ho) which says there is no relationship between organizational commitment and employee performance is rejected and (Ha) which says there is a relationship between organizational commitment and employee performance received. So that it can be concluded that there is a significant relationship between the relationship between organizational commitment and employee performance, meaning that the better the organizational commitment to employees will be followed by the better performance of employees.

The results of the second hypothesis obtained a “r” value of 0.880 with $p < 0.05$. This means (Ho) which reads there is no relationship between work motivation being rejected and employee performance rejected and (Ha) which says the relationship between work motivation and employee performance is accepted. So, it can be concluded that there is a significant relationship between the relationship between work motivation and employee performance, meaning that the better the work motivation in the employee will be followed by the better the performance.

Based on the output summary model, the results of the third hypothesis obtained an R value of 0.914 with $p < 0.05$. This means (Ho) which says there is no organizational commitment and work motivation with employee performance rejected and (Ha) which says there is a relationship between organizational commitment and work motivation with employee performance received. So, it can be concluded that there is a significant relationship with a positive direction between organizational commitment and work motivation with employee performance, meaning that the better organizational commitment and employee motivation on employees will be followed by better employee performance. The coefficient of determination or R square is 0.836, which means that organizational commitment and work motivation of employees contribute 83.6% to employee performance, the remaining 16.4% is contributed by other factors or variables.

4. Conclusions

Based on the results of data analysis and discussion that has been described, it can be concluded that:

- 1) There is a relationship between organizational commitment and the performance of employees of the head office of PT. Angkasa Pura I (PERSERO).
- 2) There is a relationship between work motivation and the performance of the employees of the head office of PT Angkasa Pura I (PERSERO).
- 3) There is a relationship between organizational commitment and work motivation with the performance of employees at PT Angkasa Pura I (PERSERO) office employees.

4.1 Suggestions

After conducting research and analyzing the research data and concluding the results of the research obtained, then the suggestions that can be given are:

4.1.1 Theoretical Suggestions

For those who want to do further research on organizational commitment and work motivation with employee performance is expected to consider other variables that can affect work motivation, grooming organizational commitment, among others, the nature of work, the work group where someone joins, the organization where he works, the general environmental situation, the applicable reward system and its application, self-esteem, personal expectations, needs, desires, job satisfaction and desired work performance.

4.1.2 Practical Advices

Based on the results of categorization which is at a high level on the scale of employee performance and work motivation. So, it is advisable to maintain work motivation. Because with the retention of employee motivation it will be able to encourage employee morale to be even better, because every employee has the ability to manage his emotions well and can use it in dealing with others, so as to create a climate of togetherness within the company. As for the level of organizational commitment that is fairly high, it is recommended to the parties involved in managing employees to maintain their policies that are already quite good and also pay more attention to the factors that can increase the level of organizational commitment by means of the welfare of their employees. Where this can ultimately stimulate the level of motivation of the work of the employees and for the smooth vision and mission of the company.

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